

Garganey (*Spatula querquedula*) in India in the Month of June

P. S. Thakker

Email: thakkerps@gmail.com

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I had visited industrial area on 6th June 2024 located on Ahmedabad-Bavala road near Rajoda village before Bavala, a company by Mr. Deepak Maroo and Mrs. Nayana Maroo. There were many birds, but to my utter

surprise I saw two birds which were Garganey duck males. I asked Shri Deepak bhai to confirm through spotting scope. And we confirmed. He took some pictures also. The time was around 4:15 pm.

Garganey at wetland in industrial area near Rajoda on Ahmedabad-Bavala Road on 6-6-2024

(Photo: Deepak Maroo)

According to Bird Count India, the Garganey is one of the common wintering ducks in the Indian subcontinent. It breeds across temperate Eurasia, much of Europe, and the Palearctic region, migrating further south to the tropics. As a migratory species, the entire population moves to Africa, India, Bangladesh, and the islands of Asia (Australasia, but not Australia) during the northern hemisphere winter. The Garganey's breeding habitat includes grasslands near shallow marshes and

steppe lakes. It is also one of the earliest arriving and latest departing ducks, often remaining in peninsular wetlands well into May. Its return migration generally begins in March-April from India, as its breeding season in these regions falls between May and June. Occasionally, some individuals may stay in India until mid-May.

Bird migration is the regular, annual journey that birds undertake between their breeding and wintering grounds. The Garganey's stay in India

typically lasts from September-October to April-May. Thakur D. R. and Ashish Mehta published a research paper in the Asian Journal of Scientific Research in 2015, noting a new migration pattern for the Garganey in the Trans-Himalayas as it explores new habitats. Over the past two centuries, migration has become increasingly difficult due to extensive habitat loss and the fragmentation of remaining habitats.

Recent records of Garganey sightings in India indicate that the bird is observed across the country even into

mid-June, suggesting the possibility that it may also be breeding in India, rather than arriving earlier than previously thought. There is a need to monitor for signs of breeding in this species, and to look for nests, eggs, and young birds.

Rosy Pastors once bred in Ahmedabad, and someone brought five young ones to Sundarvan in the Satellite area, where they were kept in a cage before later being released. Similarly, there is a possibility that Garganey may also be breeding in India.

Breeding grounds of Garganey
(Yellow-blue-blue hatching)
Source: Heinzl et.al.

Presence of Garganey in India
(Blue-yellow)
Source: Grimmett et. al.

Maps showing sightings of Garganey birds in the month of June, Sept. & Sept.-Oct.
(Source: eBird)

The lifespan of a Garganey is 20-30 years, with sexual maturity reached at one to two years. The clutch size is typically 7-9 eggs, with an incubation period of about 25-26 days, or roughly one month. The fledging period lasts around six weeks, so it takes approximately two and a half months for the young to mature into independent birds.

Shree Shanti bhai Varu reported the presence of Garganey in Gujarat at Devisar Lake on -

- On June 7, 2004, near Bhuj in Kachchh district.
- On June 2, 2019, Shree Irshad Theba reported three birds at Hala Talav in Matar, Kheda district.
- On June 19, 2021, Prashant Andharia, Kandarp Andharia, and Amir Matli reported four birds at Rohini wetland, south of Kanewal Lake in Kheda district.

Thus, Garganey has previously been reported in Kachchh and Kheda districts in the month of June. My recent sighting this June was in an industrial area in Ahmedabad district. I am considering monitoring these birds for signs of egg-laying and juveniles, health permitting. It would be beneficial to closely observe other regions—east, west, north, and south of the country—for similar activity.

I would like to acknowledge the assistance of Shri Ashok Masharu from Rajkot and D.A. Maroo in obtaining the distribution map of Garganey for the month of June and data on the spread of this bird in Gujarat during September and October, which helped in gathering information on its early arrival in the state.

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Varu S. N. (2024) personnel communication

About the Author

Dr. P.S. Thakker is a retired Research Scientist of Space Applications Center (ISRO), Ahmedabad, Gujarat. He has a vast knowledge and experience about birds of Gujarat State and has extensively travelled in the State for bird surveys. He has several scientific and popular publications to his credit.